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Effects of indoor lighting conditions and window views on occupants' well-being and behavior: a systematic review.

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Abstract. This paper reviews 49 studies that addressed how window view, daylighting, and lighting in buildings affect occupants' behavior and well-being. The systematic literature search was performed in November 2021 and focused on office and educational buildings. We quantified the number of papers per study type, study aim, and lighting condition. Predictor categories and methods for data collection were also considered. We analyzed the results according to a structure of records, defined by the number of predictors and type of outcomes from a study. We obtained 106 records. A gap in the number of studies under different lighting conditions and building types was identified. Studies under natural light and studies conducted in learning environments were fewer than studies dealing with artificial lighting in offices. A wide variety of methods for data collection was found. Artificial lighting features and correlated color temperature were the most used predictors. Based on the analysis of records, we found that 61.3% of the associations between predictors and outcomes were statistically significant. The type of effect was not reported in 3.8% of the records-meaning that approximately 35% of the records found no significant associations between predictors and outcomes.

1. Introduction

The built environment plays an essential role for the performance and well-being of occupants [1,2]. Therefore, the indoor environment must be adequate to support people's needs and meet functional demands. Over the last years, researchers have looked at the benefits of proper lighting in schools and offices [3–6], showing that the provision of daylight and the visual connection with the outdoors improve occupants' mood [7–9]. Visual stimuli such as landscapes and views with natural features have been indicated as stress-recovery [10,11] and attention-restoration boosters [12], both of which promote cognitive performance [13,14]. Furthermore, good lighting has been linked to a room's perceived attractiveness, higher satisfaction with the work environment, and work engagement [15], while an unobstructed view and controlled daylighting appeared to improve office employees' decision-making, which was translated into an economic impact based on employee salaries [16].

Regardless of the source, light triggers visual and non-visual responses, which affect human cognition, health and well-being [17]. In buildings, occupant responses to lighting are an important and growing field of research [18]. Available literature reviews have addressed the effects of indoor lighting on task performance [19], examined the evidence on lighting for work beyond visual responses [17,20–22], the effects of windows in the work environment [23], occupants' preferences towards daylighting and control systems [24] and how occupants' behavior can contribute to energy savings [25]. In this paper, we examined the available evidence on how window view, daylighting and lighting in buildings affect occupants' behavior and well-being since, in practice, they are exposed to them at the same time.

2. Method

We conducted a systematic search of studies addressing the effects of window view, daylighting, and lighting on occupants’ behavior, perception, performance, and well-being. The systematic search was performed in the Scopus database in November 2021, with the search terms presented in Figure 1. The search was done in the “title”, “abstract” and “keywords” fields. Seventy-six studies were selected according to the following criteria: i) papers presenting research results with ii) participants’ responses and iii) accounting only for daylighting, lighting, or window view assessments. This paper focused on the current evidence on occupants’ health, well-being, and behavior examined in 49 out of 76 papers [26-74].

Figure 1. Search terms

We analyzed the results following a structure of records. The number of records was defined mainly by the number of predictors and type of outcomes from a paper. Some studies presented more than one experiment; each was analyzed as separate records.

3. Results

We obtained 106 records from the 49 reviewed papers. The surveyed studies were published between 1978 and 2021 and were performed mostly in offices (n= 31) (Figure 2). Field and laboratory studies were the most frequent type (n= 17 and n= 16, respectively), while interventions were performed in 11 studies. Living-labs (n= 5) and online studies (n= 1) were less frequent -one paper presented results from laboratory and intervention-. Regarding the study aim, 20 studies looked for causality, 23 had an exploratory approach, and eight studies were descriptive. The most investigated lighting source was artificial lighting (n= 27). Combined lighting, i.e., natural and artificial light, was investigated in 18 studies, and only 4 addressed natural light. Regarding the experimental features, 22 studies used fluorescent lamps, and 11 used LED lamps. Nine studies did not report the type of lamp. Four studies addressing the effects of artificial lighting allowed a view of the outside.

Figure 2. Number of studies per building, study type and aim, and light conditions.

3.1. Predictors, outcome type and method for data collection

We identified 14 categories of predictors, presented in Figure 3. Studies examining artificial lighting and the combination of artificial and natural light used more predictors than studies using natural light. The most used categories were artificial lighting features (type of lamp, type of fixture, lighting program), correlated color temperature (CCT), window features (view features, glazing type, windowed vs. windowless), lighting type (natural vs. artificial, dynamic vs. static), horizontal illuminance (E_h) and flicker. Less used predictors were vertical illuminance, correlated color temperature + horizontal illuminances together, spectral power distribution (SPD), dynamic lighting, light color, light and blinds control (on/off, automatic vs. manual), and daylight and luminous environment (qualitative predictors).

Figure 3. Frequency of records that used each predictor and segregated by lighting condition.

Figure 4. Frequency of records that used each method of data collection.

Most of the reviewed studies ($n=43$) addressed the effects of lighting on well-being, whereas only eight studies examined participants' behavior. Two studies [61,67] examined both behavior and well-being outcomes. Three methods were used to collect data about occupants' behavior: observation (5 records), monitoring devices (4 records), and questionnaires (3 records) (Figure 4). Both monitoring devices and observation were used to report occupants' location, i.e., desk occupancy and distance from the window [71,74], and occupants' interactions with lighting and blinds [59,60,62,67]. Questionnaires measured internal responses that affected social conduct and engagement [61]. On the other hand, we

identified nine methods to register participants' well-being (Figure 4). Most studies used less invasive methods such as questionnaires (41 records). Karolinska and Epworth Sleepiness Scales- [28,29,31,33,36,42,46,49,52,53] were commonly used to assess alertness/sleepiness. Questionnaires and scales were also employed to self-assess mental effort and workload [40,46,53], mental health and stress [35,56,73], subjective well-being and quality of life [26,35,46,49,56,58,72], some symptoms such as muscular ache, headache, eyestrain and fatigue [36,39,40,44,50,53,56,61,63,67]. Affective tests were also a frequent tool (20 records) to assess subjective mood [27,29–31,33,36–38,41,44,46,55,57,61,65,69,72]. More invasive techniques as biological samples [33,34,36,43,46,50,55,57,66,72] and physiological responses like heart rate [34,40], brain activity [34,61], pupil size and eye fatigue [45,68], and body temperature [70,71] were used in 24 records. Circadian entrainment and motion, mainly during sleep, were tracked using monitoring devices [30,49,51].

Figure 5. Frequency of records with significant effect according to a) predictor and b) method for data collection.

We analyzed the type of effect, the type of predictor and the method for data collection. Overall, most of the records related to behavior and well-being resulted in a significant association between predictor(s) and outcome (62.5% and 63.8%, respectively). The significance level was not reported in 4 records. Figure 5 includes only data for predictors and data collection methods with more than two records - predictors/methods excluded are: color of light, dynamic lighting, light and blinds control, luminous environment/ actigraphy, and diary. When using as predictors the correlated color temperature (15 records), vertical illuminance (5 records), and daylight (4 records), most of the results showed significant associations. Although research in lighting has moved forward by investigating the effects of the spectral composition of light, only three records used this predictor. Window features were used in 23 records, and 69.2% of these found a significant effect on behavior and well-being. 75% of the eleven records using horizontal illuminance as a predictor found a significant effect on occupants' responses.

Questionnaires, affective tests and biological sampling seem to be the most used methods to collect data. However, 36% and 45% of the records indicated no significant result (Figure 5a). The methods showing a higher frequency of significant results used physiological responses (8 records) and observation (4 records).

3.2. Effects of indoor daylighting and lighting on occupants' behavior and well-being

3.2.1. Behavior: Preschoolers' engagement was higher when the classroom was equipped with LED lamps than fluorescent lamps [32], and pupils were closer to the window mainly because of the amount

of light and not necessarily the view [71]. Flicker was found to be correlated with the action and persistent usage of lamps with high-frequency, solid-state ballast [67] but not with social activity or arousal seeking [61]. Furthermore, the need for adjusting illumination levels was linked to controlling lights and blinds[59].

3.2.2. Well-being: Students' attention [28] and mood (affective and emotional responses) [68] were not significantly associated with the type of light bulb [28,72]; however, changes in bulb type led to marginal differences in stress hormones (cortisol) in winter [72], and students in classrooms with full-spectrum fluorescent lamps had better dental health, body growth, development, and attendance than students in classrooms with high-pressure sodium vapor lamps [64]. Workers in offices with parabolic down-lighting (750 lux, 3500 K) had more complaints about eyestrain than those in offices with lensed-indirect lighting (500 lux, 3500 K) [63]; yet, luminaire features were not associated with other physical symptoms such as headache and muscular ache. Participants exposed to an artificial skylight experienced less psychological and physiological stress, higher melatonin secretion, and decreased sympathetic nerve activity (stress-related responses) compared to fluorescent light exposure during the daytime [34]. In a windowless room with an artificial skylight and fluorescent bulbs, participants' mood, tension, and anxiety were improved under the artificial skylight [44]. Job-related stress was lower when the proportion of direct/indirect illumination delivered homogeneous light, but such feature of artificial lighting was not related to self-reported concentration or subjective well-being [56].

Participants' circadian rhythm and sleep [30], subjective alertness [50], and hormone concentration [50,66] were all affected by lighting type. When compared to static lighting, dynamic lighting decreased office workers' sleep time and reported sleep quality [30]. After 30 minutes of exposure to lamps with a blue component, melatonin was suppressed and alertness increased [50]. Variable lighting, however, was not associated with stress and mood [30], stress recovery, subjective alertness, mental health, and physical symptoms [53], or melatonin production [54]. Furthermore, children in windowless classrooms with no daylight and fluorescent lamps had considerably delayed cortisol production when compared to children in windowed classrooms, but no variations in sick leave were associated with the lighting type [66]. Seasonal daylight patterns were found to significantly impact mood, sleep activity, and hormone concentrations [41,43], while dynamic light affected the mood of participants in a simulated office setting but had no effect on melatonin secretion [55]. Under controlled conditions, flicker from fluorescent lighting had no significant influence on mood, emotional state, headache, weariness, and brainwave pattern (EEG) [61]. In contrast to high-frequency lighting, flicker from fluorescent lighting utilizing standard ballasts had a substantial (increasing) effect on self-reported weekly headaches in a controlled field trial [67].

Subjective well-being of children and adults was improved with a higher amount of nature seen from the window and greenery outside [26,35,70], whereas office workers in windowless workplaces had worse self-assessment of well-being than those in windowed offices [49]. Daylighting and greenery outside views also significantly reduced the self-assessed workload and subjective fatigue symptoms [40]. Nevertheless, differences between windowed and windowless rooms and the view content was not associated with students' mood [65], attendance [47], physical activity, or sleep [49]. Depending on the learning task, six qualitative descriptors of the luminous environment could explain students' affective responses (Clear-efficient, Uniform, Cheerful-colorful, Warm-cozy, Surprising-amazing, and Intense-brilliant). Writing-reading tasks, for example, required a light environment that was Clear-efficient, Intense-brilliant, and Uniform [37]. Different SPD (unfiltered bright light at 6300 K and 800 lux, and reduced short-wavelength with 1700 K and 800 lux eye) did not significantly affect mood or neopterin levels, an immune system activation biomarker. On the other hand, short-wavelength light had a significant effect on melatonin secretion [57].

Though cortisol secretion was reduced following exposure to white LED lamps with two CCT (3500K warm light and 6500K blue-enriched light), students exposed to blue-enriched light had lower melatonin levels, and they felt more alert and in a better mood than students exposed to warm white light [33]. Sleep quality and locomotor activity were significantly affected by switching from warm white (CCT 4000K) to blue-enriched light (8000K), which led the participants to office hours entrainment instead of natural light entrainment [51]. Fluorescent and LED lamps with a CCT of 4000K

had a positive and significant effect on office workers. They had a better mood, were less sleepy, and had less eye discomfort compared to exposure to lamps with a CCT of 3000K [36]. CCTs between 2700K and 6300K – under controlled air temperature of 22 °C- considerably boosted self-perception of alertness [39]. When compared to lower CCTs (4000K and 2900K), a high CCT (17000K) helped to preserve students’ alertness during afternoons in autumn [52] and employees’ vitality and mental health [58], though this CCT is not common for indoor lighting. Through different combinations of CCT and E_h , CCT was observed to cause seasonal changes in melatonin and cortisol concentrations, but no effects of illuminance were found [36]. Melatonin levels were higher in summer at 3000K and winter at 4000K (the opposite for cortisol). Gender influenced the effects of CCT and E_h on mood [69]. Positive mood was maintained under cool, dim light (4200K; 300 lux) and warm, bright light (2950K; 1500 lux) for female participants, while negative mood reduced at 3000K and increased at 4000K (reverse for males) [69]. CCT and E_h [48] had little effect on students’ motivation. Colored-accent light was not significantly associated with participants’ mood [38].

Studies using horizontal illuminance as a predictor resulted in six records with significant effects and five non-significant ones. Significant differences in the assessment of pleasantness were reported only in one of the two conducted experiments when a baseline condition (500 lux) was included in the illuminance pattern [High-low (from 850 lux to 250 lux) versus Low-high (from 250 lux to 850)] [29]. Though some studies concluded that changes in horizontal illuminance had no effect on participants’ alertness [29,42] or emotional state [31], it was noticed that participants’ alertness decreased under dim conditions [31], and fewer children developed myopia in classrooms with higher illuminance [48]. Participants’ mood was also lower under dim light (500 lux vertical illuminance); they were tenser and had higher mental effort than in bright (1000 lux) or self-selected illuminance [46]. In Figure 6, we present the type of effect reported in the records of each study.

Figure 6. Frequency of records per outcome category and predictor, separated by type of effect-numbers are indicating the reference.

4. Conclusions

We reviewed studies addressing the effects of window views, daylighting, and lighting on occupants' behavior and well-being. The selected papers were found by limited search terms and focused on research conducted in offices and educational buildings. Thus, papers that did not contain any building-related keywords were not caught by the search, and it is a limitation of this review. Nevertheless, we identified a gap in the number of studies under each lighting condition and building type. Studies under natural light and studies conducted in learning environments were fewer than studies dealing with artificial lighting in offices.

Through various light-related predictors and methods for data collection, the studies showed that indoor lighting conditions and window views can affect occupants' behavior and well-being. A wide variety of methods for data collection was identified, mainly in studies on well-being. Based on the analysis of records, we found that 61.3% of the reported results were statistically significant - the type of effect was not reported in 3.8% of the records-meaning that approximately 35% of the results found no significant effect. Changes in the artificial lighting features (e.g., type of lamp, type of fixture, lighting program) and correlated color temperature were commonly used, mainly in studies focusing on artificial sources. Whereas research on the effects of the spectral composition of indoor lighting is growing, in our limited literature search, only three studies used SPD as a predictor. Also, studies under both natural and artificial light should carefully consider and/or control the view to the outside. A combined effect on occupants' responses is particularly expected for windows, which are accountable for both daylight and the outside view unless covered with translucent materials.

5. References

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